

1 Hypothetical Extraction Method in Life
2 Cycle Assessment: Method and Uses

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14 Contribution Analysis, Hotspot Analysis, Input Output Analysis (IOA), Industrial Ecology

15

16 Abstract

17 Hypothetical Extraction Method (HEM) is an approach in Input Output Analysis (IOA) used to
18 assess the effects of ‘*target*’ economic sectors have on other sectors. If we interpret HEM in
19 a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) context, HEM could be described as ‘assessing the
20 contribution of processes (or groups of processes) to the impact of other processes’,
21 making this another potential Contribution Analysis (CA) approach. In this study, we
22 introduce HEM in LCA and demonstrate how HEM may provide different insights compared
23 to the already existing CA approaches in two example case-studies. We do this by showing
24 how HEM may be applied in LCA in four steps: 1) defining a scenario for extraction, 2)
25 extracting *target* processes, 3) calculating results for the *original* and ‘*remaining*’ system and
26 4) calculating results for the *target* processes. We then demonstrate HEM in LCA using
27 different example case-studies and compare HEM against other CA approaches. We also
28 demonstrate process contributions to the *target* and *remaining* sections, allowing deeper
29 insight into results. With this study we have shown how and when HEM can be a useful
30 approach for CA in cases where current CA approaches may be lacking, providing an
31 additional CA approach to the LCA practitioner in understanding impacts from their systems.

32 Abbreviations

CA	Contribution Analysis
CH ₄	Methane
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CO ₂ eq.	Carbon dioxide equivalent
CPC	Central Product Classification
EF	Elementary Flow
FU	Functional Unit
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HEM	Hypothetical Extraction Method
IOA	Input Output Analysis
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
SI	Supplementary Information

33

34 1. Introduction

35 Hypothetical Extraction Method (HEM) is a method in Input Output Analysis (IOA) used to
36 assess the effects economic sectors have on other sectors (Hertwich et al., 2024) and stems
37 from the 1960s (Dietzenbacher & Lahr, 2013; Miller, 1966; Miller & Lahr, 2001; Paelinck et
38 al., 1965). To perform HEM, a counterfactual scenario is created where the ‘*target*’ sector
39 (Dente et al., 2018) is extracted from the IOA model and results are re-calculated. The
40 difference between the *original* result and the HEM scenario is considered to be caused by
41 the extracted *target* sector.

42 HEM can be used for many different use-cases such as assessing the contribution from
43 regions in multi-regional IO or industry sectors (Beaufils et al., 2023; Berthet & Fusacchia,
44 2024; Gallego & Lenzen, 2005; Hanaka et al., 2022; Tokito et al., 2020), assessing the
45 ‘importance’ of an economic sector to other sectors in terms of consumption (Miller & Lahr,
46 2001) or assessing the effect of disruptive events (Dietzenbacher et al., 2019; Haddad et al.,
47 2021). More directly related to Industrial Ecology, HEM has also been used to assess the
48 contribution of sectors to carbon footprints of products and consumption baskets (Hertwich,
49 2021; Rasul & Hertwich, 2023). For an extensive overview of the method examples of use we
50 refer to Miller & Lahr (2001), Dietzenbacher & Lahr (2013) and Hertwich et al. (2024).

51 Even though IOA and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) have similar mathematical structures,
52 HEM is not used in LCA, though their similar structures could make this possible.

53 If we loosely interpret the goal of HEM ‘assessing the impact of sectors on other sectors’ to
54 an LCA context, we find something like ‘assessing the impact of processes (or groups of
55 processes) on other processes’. This could be interpreted as similar to Contribution
56 Analysis (CA) (what is the contribution of x to the total?) (Guinée et al., 2002; Heijungs &
57 Kleijn, 2001). Through the extraction, this would assess not only the contribution of a
58 process’ direct contribution (Srocka & Montiel, 2021) but also all consumption of that
59 process, meaning it would include indirect contributions as well (Reinhard et al., 2016; van
60 der Meide et al., 2025).

61 Other CA approaches that assess both direct and indirect contributions are First-Tier CA
62 (van der Meide et al., 2025), assessing contributions of products feeding into the Functional
63 Unit (FU). Life Cycle Stage CA (van der Meide et al., 2025), dividing the system into relevant
64 sections of the supply chain such as ‘production’ and ‘use’. And Path/Sankey CA (Srocka &
65 Montiel, 2021), showing the ‘path’ contributions take to the FU. While these approaches
66 each have their own unique strengths, they cannot be used to assess large groups of
67 processes, for example industry sectors or regions effectively.

68 CA approaches could also be applied to systematically assess system-wide changes,
69 applying it at another level than CA. Some examples are: Finding ‘causer’ and ‘connector’
70 processes in LCI databases (Reinhard et al., 2016), where these processes either have direct
71 (Srocka & Montiel, 2021) or indirect (van der Meide et al., 2025) contributions, respectively.
72 Two other examples are the identification of important capital goods in an LCI database
73 (Frischknecht et al., 2007) and an analysis of abiotic resources in an LCI database (Rørbech
74 et al., 2014).

75 While there are already various approaches to assessing indirect contributions in LCA,
76 approaches to assess the indirect contribution from large groups of processes, such as
77 sectors or regions do not currently exist.

78 The objective of this study is to introduce HEM in LCA as a new approach to CA and
79 demonstrate how HEM may provide different insights compared to the already existing CA
80 approaches. We formalize the method in LCA and demonstrate with a simplified case study
81 how it may be used and how results may be interpreted. Next, we compare it against other
82 approaches with the simplified case study. After this, we also demonstrate HEM using two
83 examples using the ecoinvent LCI database (Wernet et al., 2016) to simulate a more realistic
84 case study. Finally, we discuss how HEM in LCA may help LCA practitioners to find new
85 insights and discuss the nuances between different CA approaches.

86 2. Method

87 2.1. Notation

88 We demonstrate the approach in vectorized format. We use *italic lower case* for scalar
89 values, **bold lower case** for vectors and **BOLD UPPER CASE** for matrices. Column
90 vectors are written as \mathbf{v} , while row vectors are written as \mathbf{v}^T . All results presented are
91 rounded, we refer to the excel file SI 2 for unrounded results.

92 2.2. Mathematical structure of LCA

93 We shortly introduce the mathematical structure of LCA based on Heijungs & Suh (2002) and
94 the SI of van der Meide et al. (2025). LCA is generally done as IO-LCA or as process-LCA
95 (Heijungs et al., 2022). In this study the focus is on process-LCA where applying IOA
96 methods has traditionally been challenging or impossible (Heijungs et al., 2022; Suh &
97 Heijungs, 2007), we also shortly discuss their differences in SI 1.1. We refer to Heijungs &
98 Suh (2002) for an extensive introduction to the mathematical background of LCA and van der
99 Meide et al. (2025) for a more extensive treatment of CA in LCA.

100 We start with the known information; \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{q}^T . Here, \mathbf{A} is the technology matrix, \mathbf{B} is
101 the Elementary Flow (EF) matrix, \mathbf{f} is the functional unit (FU) vector and \mathbf{q}^T is the
102 characterization vector.

103 The technology matrix \mathbf{A} has processes as columns, with inputs (consumption) to that
104 process as negative values and the produced product as a positive value for output. Each
105 row in \mathbf{A} shows how much of the product/service the given process produces is consumed
106 in other processes. The EF matrix \mathbf{B} shows which interventions each process causes as an
107 EF in the environment as columns. It has the same amount of columns as \mathbf{A} .

108 First, a scaling vector \mathbf{s} is calculated, this represents how many times each process needs
109 to produce its product to fulfil the FU expressed by \mathbf{f} :

$$\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{s} \rightarrow \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{f} \quad (1)$$

110 Next, \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{s} can be multiplied to calculate the inventory results vector \mathbf{g} , which shows all
111 EFs emitted or consumed to fulfill the FU \mathbf{f} :

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{s} \quad (2)$$

112

113 Finally, the inventory results vector is characterized to a characterized result h by
114 multiplying by the characterization vector \mathbf{q} :

$$h = \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{g} \quad (3)$$

115 Or:

$$h = \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{B} \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{f} \quad (4)$$

116

117 As the results from eq. (2) and (3) only show one characterized result for every FU and every
118 impact category, these don't show any insights into what processes or EFs contribute to the
119 total result. These results can be disaggregated to show which process causes each EF for
120 the given FU, turning the inventory into a contribution matrix $\mathbf{g} \rightarrow \mathbf{G}$ (Srocka & Montiel, 2021).

121 To calculate the contribution matrix, the \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{q} vector are diagonalized. Diagonalizing
122 means putting the values of the respective vector on the diagonal of a square $\mathbf{0}$ matrix of the
123 same size.

124 This leads to adjustments of eq. (2) and (3) below:

$$\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{B} \mathit{diag}(\mathbf{s}) \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathit{diag}(\mathbf{q}) \mathbf{G} \quad (6)$$

125

126 Through the above adjustment, **G** and **H** become matrices with a value (*g* for inventory or *h*
127 for characterized results) for each process as a column and each EF as a row.

128 2.3. Example case

129 We demonstrate HEM in LCA based on a simple case study example of four processes; coal
130 mining, electricity production, iron ore mining and steel production. We show the system in
131 Figure 1 and define the inventory of these processes in Table 1. We use this simplified
132 example system to demonstrate the principles of HEM in LCA, show example results and
133 compare similar approaches to HEM using this example system. We will focus primarily on
134 the production of '1kg steel' as FU, it will be make clear in instances where this is not the
135 case. As an impact category, we use climate change (GWP 100) from the IPCC (2022),
136 characterizing CO₂ emissions as 1 kgCO₂eq./kg and CH₄ emissions as 29.8 kgCO₂eq./kg.

137 We strongly emphasize that this example is exclusively for the demonstration of HEM and is
138 not meant to represent reality nor to assess the actual impact of processes within this
139 system.

140
141 *Figure 1. Product system for the example case study.*

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146

147 Table 1. Inventory table for the example case study, showing functional flow, intermediate flows and EF per process.

Process name	Functional flow (Product/Service)	Intermediate flows	Elementary flows
Coal mining	Coal: 1 kg	Electricity: 0.04 kWh Steel: 0.001 kg	CO ₂ : 0.05 kg CH ₄ : 0.01 kg
Electricity production	Electricity: 1 kWh	Coal: 0.4 kg Steel: 0.001 kg	CO ₂ : 0.8 kg
Iron ore mining	Iron ore: 1 kg	Electricity: 0.1 kWh Steel: 0.001 kg	
Steel production	Steel: 1 kg	Coal: 0.8 kg Iron ore: 2 kg	CO ₂ : 1.6 kg

148

149 Based on Table 1 above, we get the following technology matrix A , EF matrix B and
 150 characterization vector q^T from the description above:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.4 & 0 & -0.8 \\ -0.04 & 1 & -0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -2 \\ -0.001 & -0.001 & -0.001 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.05 & 0.8 & 0 & 1.6 \end{bmatrix} \quad q^T = \begin{bmatrix} 29.8 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

151

152 Where the rows/columns from the top/left in technology matrix A are ‘Coal mining’,
 153 ‘Electricity Production’, ‘Iron ore mining’ and ‘Steel production’. For the EF matrix B and
 154 characterization vector q^T , we first list CH₄ and then CO₂.

155 2.4. Applying HEM to LCA

156 In general the steps of applying HEM in IOA is that a counterfactual (hypothetical) scenario
 157 is created where one or more *target* sectors are removed (extracted) and results are re-
 158 calculated without for the ‘*remaining*’ sectors. The difference between the *original* result
 159 and the *remaining* result is the effect from the extracted *target* sector.

160 The goal of HEM in IOA is to assess the effect of a sector on other sectors in a final result can
 161 be translated to the context of LCA. Here, the goal becomes ‘assessing the contribution a
 162 process (or group of processes) has on the final result from the FU’. We develop HEM in LCA
 163 further with this goal in mind. As the mathematical structure differs, our approach is slightly
 164 different as well.

165 To apply HEM to LCA, we need to take 4 steps:

- 166 1. Define an HEM scenario
- 167 2. Extract the processes
- 168 3. Calculate the results for the *original* and *remaining* system
- 169 4. Calculate the results for the *target* processes

170 In the further text, in all cases that could apply to one or multiple processes, we will refer to
171 this as ‘processes’ in plural for brevity. In specific instances where only one or the other is
172 meant, it will be made clear.

173 We emphasize that the ‘H’ in HEM stands for Hypothetical, meaning that we do not truly
174 assume that the *target* processes would suddenly ‘not exist’, the extraction is rather a tool
175 to assess the contribution of the *target* and/or *remaining* processes to the total result.

176 All information to replicate this approach conceptually or in small product-systems can be
177 found in this article and its SI, the code make use of this approach or to replicate it using
178 Brightway2 (Mutel, 2017) on real-world systems is provided in van der Meide (2025).

179 2.4.1. HEM scenario definition

180 First, the practitioner must choose *target* processes to extract. The *target* processes can be
181 any set of processes of interest for the question the practitioner is trying to answer. This
182 grouping can be based on the process metadata (information describing the process, like
183 name, product, location or an industry sector (e.g. as given in ecoinvent metadata (Wernet
184 et al., 2016)). The processes should have some relationship to each other that makes them
185 relevant to extract together. For example, a practitioner could choose all ecoinvent
186 processes with the Central Product Classification (CPC) (UN, 2015) Division ‘14: Metal ores’
187 and they could assess the contribution of products classified as such to the final result.
188 Another example could be, if the practitioner would choose all processes with the location
189 ‘NL’ in an LCI database, the practitioner could assess the impact processes in the
190 Netherlands have on the final result, mirroring the regional example Miller and Lahr (2001)
191 give.

192 2.4.2. Extracting processes

193 After defining an HEM scenario, we calculate the scaling vector \mathbf{s} (following eq. (1)) for the
194 *original* system and the *remaining* system. As Miller and Lahr (2001) discuss, there are
195 several options to extract sectors. In process-LCA, the list of options is more limited
196 because we use a different mathematical model. The mathematical format of process-
197 based LCA (Heijungs et al., 2022) makes it impossible to calculate results for any FU if the
198 reference flow of any process is ‘0’ (not producing anything), this reduces the amount of
199 options we can use compared to Miller and Lahr (2001). We discuss this further in SI 1.2.
200 Taking these limitations into account, the following four options in Table 2 are possible
201 approaches to HEM in LCA with corresponding case numbers from Miller and Lahr (2001) for
202 comparison.

203 *Table 2. Options to extract processes for HEM in LCA. The numbering of the cases is the same as in Miller and Lahr (2001).*

Case	Description
1	Extracting the processes from the technology matrix, decreasing its size (deleting both the rows and columns).
2a	Extracting both <i>consumers</i> (row values) and <i>consumption</i> (column values) of the <i>target</i> processes, resulting in processes that are both un-used and 'empty' (replacing all process flow values except reference flow with 0).
3a	Extracting all <i>consumers</i> (row values) of the <i>target</i> processes in the technology matrix, resulting in processes that are un-used (replacing all process flows <i>from</i> this process with 0).
3b	Extracting all <i>consumption</i> (column values) of the <i>target</i> processes in the technology matrix, resulting in 'empty' processes (replacing all process flows <i>to</i> this process with 0).

204

205 While the first option (case 1) seems most intuitive, this option could be potentially
 206 challenging as it changes the size of matrices, making it harder to keep consistent links
 207 between the *original* system and the HEM scenario for comparison later.

208 The second option (2a) may seem like a good option as it 'isolates' the processes and
 209 maintains the matrix sizes. Though making the extracted processes have 'no consumption'
 210 is not ideal as the *target* processes would always have '0' impact due to not consuming
 211 anything.

212 The third option (3a), would (similar to case 2a) also 'isolate' the processes. However,
 213 if one or more of the extracted processes in question is part of the FU, this would now still
 214 show what that process would consume from the *remaining* system (or from other extracted
 215 process), thus being a better representation for all processes that could be in the FU.

216 The last option (3b) would still 'isolate' the *target* processes, and remove their
 217 associated impacts to the system, this makes the results equivalent to option 2a in LCA.
 218 However, as explained with case 3a, this form of isolation would not be representative in
 219 case processes in the FU are part of the extracted processes.

220 Whenever the FU is not part of the *target* processes (such as the example used here), all four
 221 cases lead to the same result in LCA, as discussed and demonstrated in SI 1.2 and SI 2.2.
 222 Only in cases where the FU is part of the *target* processes can results differ, we suggest
 223 making use of Case 3a as we can still differentiate between direct and indirect contributions
 224 from the extracted *target* processes by combining HEM with process CA. The implications
 225 of all four cases with the FU in the *target* processes are discussed in SI 1.3. In the remainder
 226 of the text, we make use of Case 3a as the default.

227 While in IOA the interest often lies in the technology matrix, in LCA, the interaction of the
 228 processes with the environment is very important to consider as well. This means that with
 229 HEM in LCA we also extract the EF matrix **B**.

230 We show the extraction of ‘electricity production’ from our example system below. This
 231 gives us the *remaining* system \mathbf{A}^* and \mathbf{B}^* , marked with a ‘*’ to show these are changed. We
 232 also mark the changed items in yellow. Note here that we mirror the superscript notation for
 233 *remaining* and *target* systems (*, o) of Hertwich et al. (2024) for consistency:

Matrix	<i>Original system</i>	Matrix	<i>Remaining system case 3a</i>
$\mathbf{A} =$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.4 & 0 & -0.8 \\ -0.04 & 1 & -0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -2 \\ -0.001 & -0.001 & -0.001 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$\mathbf{A}^* =$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.4 & 0 & -0.8 \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -2 \\ -0.001 & -0.001 & -0.001 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$\mathbf{B} =$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.05 & 0.8 & 0 & 1.6 \end{bmatrix}$	$\mathbf{B}^* =$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & \mathbf{0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0.05 & \mathbf{0} & 0 & 1.6 \end{bmatrix}$

234

235 2.4.3. Results for the Original and Remaining system

236 With the extraction complete, the *remaining* scaling vector \mathbf{s}^* can be calculated (following
 237 eq. (1) again) from the \mathbf{A}^* technology matrix. Where \mathbf{s}^* is a *partial scaling vector* of the FU for
 238 the *remaining* system. A partial scaling vector represents a partial fulfilment of the *original*
 239 FU, where all partial scaling vectors together fulfil the full FU (van der Meide et al., 2025).

240 We can calculate the inventory for both the *original* (\mathbf{g}) and *remaining* system (\mathbf{g}^*) with eq.
 241 (2). We can logically take this a step further to now calculate characterized results with eq.
 242 (3) for the *original* (\mathbf{h}) and *remaining* (\mathbf{h}^*) systems.

243 2.4.4. Results for the Target processes

244 So far, we have calculated results for the *remaining* processes (the hypothetical extraction),
 245 we take this a step further to find results for the *target* processes as well, which is the goal
 246 of HEM. As we discussed above, the scaling vector \mathbf{s}^* is a partial scaling vector, making
 247 \mathbf{g}^* the partial inventory. As our FU did not change, the difference between the partial
 248 inventory and the *original* inventory will be caused by the extraction of the *target* processes. We
 249 can calculate the *target* inventory by subtracting the partial inventory \mathbf{g}^* from the *original*
 250 inventory \mathbf{g} :

$$251 \quad \mathbf{g}^o = \mathbf{g} - \mathbf{g}^* \quad (7)$$

251

252 Note that eq. (7) can also be applied to a diagonalized instance of \mathbf{g} , as \mathbf{G} , this is shown in
 253 the example later. We can then calculate the characterized results \mathbf{h}^o for the *target* as well
 254 by again using eq. (3).

255 In the context of HEM in LCA, the inventory and characterized results of the *target* system
 256 should be interpreted as the EFs or impact caused by the products or services provided by

257 the *target* processes. This would include both the direct and indirect EFs or impacts. In other
258 words, all the EFs that are caused to produce all intermediate flows of the *target* throughout
259 the entire system (in the example, the CH₄ emitted to mine the coal to produce the
260 electricity). The inventory and characterized results of the *remaining* system are from
261 everything else. We show how this may be interpreted in the results section.

262 Following from eq. (7), if we sum the partial *target* and *remaining* inventory vectors, we still
263 have the *original* inventory vector ($\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{g}^* + \mathbf{g}^o$). While this may seem trivial, it is important
264 to note, as this does guarantee that this approach is not double (or under) counting for a
265 single extraction. By splitting the inventory into two partial inventories, we can assess the
266 contribution of both the extracted processes and the *remaining* system to the full result.

267 Alternatively, applying eq. (5) to \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{s}^* and then applying eq. (7) allows us to assess the
268 contribution matrices of both the *target* processes and *remaining* system, as well as their
269 characterized versions by applying eq. (6). These last steps allow us to assess contributions
270 to the partial *target* processes and *remaining* system.

271 Finally, a careful reader may have noticed we do not apply eq. (7) to the scaling vector \mathbf{s} but
272 to the inventory \mathbf{g} . We do this as we also change the EF matrix \mathbf{B} , which would affect the
273 inventory independent of the scaling vector. This detail is discussed further in SI 1.4.

274 We provide a visual overview of the last three steps in Figure 2.

2: Extract processes 3: Calculate Original & Remaining 4: Calculate Target

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276

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Figure 2. Graphical overview of calculation steps for HEM. First, processes are extracted (blue), next, the original and remaining system are calculated (yellow) and finally, the target is calculated (pink).

278 3. Results

279 3.1. Interpreting HEM results

280 For our example case, we extract the *target* process ‘electricity production’ as shown in the
281 method and calculate the results for a FU of ‘1kg steel’.

282 We calculate the following scaling vectors from equation (1). Note that values are rounded:

$$283 \mathbf{s}^T = [0.9 \quad 0.24 \quad 2... \quad 1. \dots] \quad \mathbf{s}^{*T} = [0.8 \quad 0 \quad 2. \dots \quad 1. \dots]$$

284 Based on these scaling vectors, we calculate the following LCI from eqs. (5) and (7) and
285 characterized contribution matrices with eq. (6):

$$286 \mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.009 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.045 & 0.189 & 0 & 1.605 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{G}^* = \begin{bmatrix} 0.008 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.04 & 0 & 0 & 1.604 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{G}^o = \begin{bmatrix} 0.001 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.005 & 0.189 & 0 & 0.001 \end{bmatrix}$$
$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.267 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.045 & 0.189 & 0 & 1.605 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{H}^* = \begin{bmatrix} 0.239 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.04 & 0 & 0 & 1.604 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{H}^o = \begin{bmatrix} 0.028 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.005 & 0.189 & 0 & 0.001 \end{bmatrix}$$

287 Note again that as \mathbf{G}^* , \mathbf{G}^o and \mathbf{H}^* , \mathbf{H}^o are partial results, they sum to the total result \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{H}
288 respectively. The results above are rounded, the full results are available in SI 2.1.

289 As \mathbf{G}^o represents the partial inventory of the *target* processes, it does not just represent the
290 direct, but also indirect elementary flows of processes in the system. This is because we
291 ‘extracted’ not only the production of electricity, but also all production (coal, steel, iron ore
292 for the steel etc.) needed for the production of that electricity, thus also including indirect
293 impacts.

294 In HEM, the *target* processes never contribute to the *remaining* impact, but the *remaining*
295 processes can contribute to the *target* impact. We show the results for the *target* and
296 *remaining* system and the direct contributions to both in Figure 3 A. Here, we can see that
297 the HEM *target* ‘electricity’ is contributing 10.58% of the impact to climate change to steel.
298 In the first row of Table 3 we see this contribution is made up of both 8.98% direct
299 contribution for ‘electricity production’, as well from indirect contributions from ‘coal
300 mining’ and ‘steel production’ needed to produce that electricity. For the *remaining* system,
301 the contributions are from ‘coal mining’ and ‘steel production’ without any contribution from
302 ‘electricity production’.

303

304

305 Table 3. Direct and Indirect contribution results of 'electricity' or 'electricity production' for 'steel production'. Percentages
 306 have been rounded to 2 digits to show differences, complete results are available in SI 2.1.

	Electricity production/ Electricity	Coal mining	Steel production	Connector	Total
HEM Target	8.98%	1.57%	0.03%		10.58%
Electricity life cycle stage	8.96%	1.56%	0.01%		10.52%
Path (electricity)	8.84%	1.71%	0.02%		10.58%
Causer/Connector	8.98%			1.74%	10.72%

307

308

309 Figure 3. Contribution Analysis results for different approaches for the production of 1kg steel and the
 310 extraction/contribution of 'electricity'. Top numbers are the climate change impact in kgCO₂eq., the bottom numbers are
 311 in percentage contribution. **A:** Contribution of both the target processes and remaining system. Also showing the process
 312 contributions to the target and remaining system. **B:** Process contributions. **C:** Process contributions to Life Cycle Stages.
 313 **D:** Path contributions at 'electricity production'. **E:** Causer and Connector contributions for 'electricity production'. Note
 314 that causer contributions are the same as process contributions.

315 3.1.1. Extracting the Functional Unit

316 It could happen in an analysis that the practitioner wants to extract the processes that
 317 provide the FU. With case 3a we use for the extraction, this is possible. We demonstrate this
 318 with the example system by now taking '1kWh of Electricity' as a FU.

319 Intuitively one may assume that the contribution would just be 100%, as the extracted
 320 process is causing 100% of its direct and indirect contribution. However, the results show a

321 different picture when using case 3a (though we do find the assumed 100% contribution
322 when using the other extraction cases). Through the extraction of the direct impacts (in B^*)
323 and consumption of electricity by the other processes (in A^*), we have created a situation
324 where our *remaining* system contribution would show the impact of everything *needed* for
325 the production of electricity, except for the electricity itself. The *target* would now show the
326 direct contribution of ‘Electricity production’ and the indirect contribution of all electricity
327 that would be consumed in the system to produce that electricity. Extracting the FU is the
328 only instance where case 3a is different from cases 2a and 3b in terms of results. We discuss
329 this further and show results for this in SI 1.3 and show results for all cases where the FU is
330 extracted in SI 2.3.

331 3.2. Comparison with other approaches

332 For our comparison with other approaches, we extract ‘electricity production’ and use ‘1kg
333 Steel’ as FU. Full results are presented in SI 2.1.

334 3.2.1. Process contributions

335 When comparing HEM results against direct process contributions (Figure 3 B), we see that
336 applying HEM to ‘electricity production’ not only accounts for the direct, but also indirect
337 impacts of electricity production.

338 3.2.2. Life Cycle Stage Contribution Analysis

339 For the Life Cycle Stage contributions (van der Meide et al., 2025), we assume a life cycle
340 stage consisting of the process ‘electricity production’ only. We show the process
341 contributions to the life cycle stage and remainder of the system in Figure 3 C. We note the
342 total impact is still the same (no double counting) but that the contribution of the life cycle
343 stage is lower. The exact differences *within* the life cycle stage are shown in Table 3. The
344 difference with HEM is because the partial-FU of the life cycle stage only considers the direct
345 use of electricity for the production of the FU. Other ‘indirect’ use, e.g. the electricity needed
346 to produce coal to produce electricity is excluded. This is an important conceptual
347 difference between HEM and Life Cycle Stage contributions, where HEM completely
348 ‘isolates’ the processes through ‘extraction’ and Life Cycle Stage contributions instead
349 consider direct use for the FU only.

350 3.2.3. Path Contribution Analysis

351 For Path contributions (Srocka & Montiel, 2021), the impact of ‘Electricity’ (Figure 3 D) is the
352 same compared to HEM. In this case, we see that a lower contribution is attributed to
353 ‘Electricity production’, while a higher contribution is attributed to ‘Coal mining’ in Table 3.
354 Through the extraction of processes, HEM effectively breaks infinite loops between

355 processes (e.g. coal is needed to produce electricity and electricity is needed to produce
356 coal), where Path contributions does not, which leads to different attributions of
357 contribution. As shown in Table 3, the contribution from ‘Electricity production’ is lower than
358 the direct process contribution of the same process, we discuss this in more detail in SI 1.6.

359 As long as a singular process is extracted, the total result will be the same, however, when
360 multiple processes are extracted, results may differ, as these could (indirectly) affect each
361 other, this would lead to double counting in Path contributions. We discuss this in some
362 more detail in SI 1.6.

363 3.2.4. Causer and Connector Contribution Analysis

364 Causer and Connector contributions (Reinhard et al., 2016) are more useful for systematic
365 analysis of databases than ‘regular’ CA, but here we use this approach to assess the
366 contributions of electricity production. We find two major differences compared to HEM:
367 Firstly, we find higher contributions compared to HEM (Figure 3 E). Secondly we find only the
368 aggregated contribution for ‘connector’ (indirect contributions), without any possible
369 disaggregation of the processes that are in this group, which may not be ideal in CA.

370 While the direct contributions are the same (given that the FU amount is the same as the
371 amount of product produced by that process), the indirect contributions are higher.
372 Reinhard et al. (2016) point to double counting of their method for connector contributions,
373 while they did not consider this a major issue for their specific use case, double counting
374 should be avoided in CA.

375 3.3. Applying HEM using ecoinvent

376 Having demonstrated this approach to a small example, we now demonstrate HEM with two
377 simple (but much larger) examples using ecoinvent v3.11 (Wernet et al., 2016). The code for
378 this example is available at (van der Meide, 2025). We show the contribution of the mining
379 sector and of China as a location to the production of copper. As a Functional unit, we use
380 1 kg of ‘copper cathode’ from ‘Market for copper, cathode, GLO’. We extract processes
381 based on metadata, for ‘mining’ we use the CPC classification ‘14: Metal ores’ (and
382 processes with underlying classifications), for the location China we use the ecoinvent
383 locations starting with CN as metadata. We do two different extractions based on the mining
384 classification and location data. To assess climate change impact, we use the GWP 100
385 method from the IPCC (2022). The example of the mining sector is demonstrated below, the
386 example of extracting China is shown in SI 1.7.2.

387 Applying HEM to this example, we find the results in Figure 4 A. Here, we see that the *target*
388 ‘mining’ contributes about 39% of the impact. To gain further insight, we then assess the

389 process group contributions to both the *target* and *remaining* groups, grouping the
 390 processes by the reference product names. This shows us that both the *target* and *remaining*
 391 sectors are heavily affected by contributions from ‘electricity’, though the production of this
 392 electricity may happen in entirely different locations for the *target* and *remaining* systems.

393 We now compare HEM to grouped process contributions. The process group contributions
 394 only show the direct contributions. In Figure 4 B we have two groups; the processes in the
 395 *target* and *remaining* groups. Here, we find that the *target* ‘mining’ has almost no direct
 396 contribution. In Figure 4 C we also compare against the three main process groups and a
 397 remainder, grouped based on reference product. Here we find no mining processes. This
 398 shows us that while considering direct contributions may show *sources* of contributions,
 399 indirect contributions can show how these contributions connect to the FU (Reinhard et al.,
 400 2016).

401 From these results, a producer of copper may conclude that while they may be able to
 402 switch to more sustainable sources of electricity for their production processes, a large part
 403 of the electricity related impacts come from mining.

404

405 *Figure 4. Contribution Analysis results for different approaches for the production of 1kg ‘copper, cathode’ and the*
 406 *extraction/contribution of ‘Metal, ores’ in ecoinvent. The bottom numbers are in percentage contribution. A: Contribution*
 407 *of both the target processes and remaining system. Also showing the grouped process contributions to the target and*
 408 *remaining system. Grouped by reference product name, showing highest three contributing process groups and ‘rest’. B:*
 409 *Grouped process contributions, grouped by ‘target’ and ‘remaining’. C: Grouped process contributions, grouped by*
 410 *reference product name, showing highest three contributing process groups and ‘rest’.*

411 Comparing approaches that show indirect contributions becomes more challenging in
 412 larger examples. Path Contributions can be calculated and are shown in SI 1.7.1. While
 413 calculating these results is easy, interpretation becomes complex as there are many
 414 production routes from ‘ore’ to the final product for the production of copper, some

415 consisting of multiple processes in a chain. Combining these into a single ‘minging’ group is
416 difficult due to interdependencies of these processes. For Life Cycle Stage contributions,
417 we run into the same issue, where a life cycle stage would need to be defined for each
418 production route, making this not only time consuming but also error-prone to ensure the
419 life cycle stages don’t overlap in this complex supply chain.

420 4. Discussion

421 Above, we have shown how HEM may be applied in LCA through: 1) defining a scenario, 2)
422 extracting processes, 3) calculating results for the *original* and *remaining* system and 4)
423 calculating results for the *target* processes. We have discussed interpretation of HEM
424 results and have compared HEM against other CA approaches. That said, we want to
425 emphasize that this should be considered as an additional approach for CA that may be
426 useful in specific cases, not a replacement of existing ones.

427 The main advantage of HEM in LCA is that it allows practitioners to assess contributions of
428 processes anywhere in the system, independent of their ‘network’ relationship between
429 each other in the supply chain but also independent of their relationship to the FU. We have
430 shown that this may be a useful approach when making use of large LCI databases and many
431 processes may need to be assessed with our example using the ecoinvent LCI database
432 (Wernet et al., 2016). Further uses could be to identify highly contributing sectors or
433 countries (demonstrated in SI 1.7.2), or this could be identifying suppliers or materials, that
434 are important to a manufacturer.

435 4.1. Other applications for HEM

436 Another use-case of HEM may mirror that of Reinhard et al. (2016) where HEM can be used
437 to systematically assess contributions from processes (or groups of processes) to other
438 processes in an LCI database. These results could be used to prioritize database
439 improvements while not double-counting impacts.

440 Furthermore, HEM could also be applied partially in two ways: 1) Reducing the ‘extracted’
441 amounts instead of completely removing them, making HEM this very similar to Sensitivity
442 Analysis (Heijungs & Kleijn, 2001) (e.g. extracting half of the use of electricity). 2) Targeting
443 the extraction of single uses of a product instead of all uses (e.g. the extraction of electricity
444 use in coal mining), making the extraction more targeted. Both partial approaches may be
445 useful, though the use-cases for this may be limited and it would be very important to
446 carefully document what is extracted.

447 4.2. Comparison with other CA approaches

448 Life Cycle Stage CA bears a lot of similarity to HEM and both approaches avoid double
449 counting, though the main difference is that HEM considers the use of all of the reference
450 product from the *target* processes, where Life Cycle Stage CA only considers the direct use
451 from the FU. Similarly, Path contributions are also close in results, though Path CA under-
452 counts the contribution compared to process CA, implying that the contributions would be
453 lower than they actually are.

454 As we have shown, both Life Cycle Stage CA and Path CA quickly become challenging to
455 apply and interpret once many processes are involved. This use-case is where HEM
456 becomes particularly useful; large systems and many *target* processes, especially if the
457 direct ‘supply chain’ link between the FU and the *target* processes may be unclear.

458 Another comparison we made was with ‘causer’ and ‘connector’ contributions (Reinhard et
459 al., 2016), here we find that we can calculate the same kind of results, but without double
460 counting. Furthermore, HEM can apply this method to groups of processes, making it more
461 useful for larger systems, where the contribution of a single process is likely to be low.
462 Another advantage to HEM is that we are able to apply process contributions to the
463 *remaining* system and *target* processes, allowing additional insight into results that was
464 previously not possible.

465 One approach to HEM in LCA that we have not yet discussed but is technically similar is how
466 Volkart et al. (2018) extract processes from their system to avoid double counting in a
467 coupling of LCA with Partial Equilibrium models. While their stated goal is entirely different
468 (avoiding double counting), they effectively use a similar approach (extracting processes
469 similar to case 3a). Another difference is that we also explore the use of process
470 contributions within the *remaining* system and *target* processes to gain more insight into
471 results.

472 4.3. Limitations of HEM

473 CA is generally applied to answer one of two kinds of questions: ‘What entities contribute to
474 the total?’ and ‘What is the contribution of this entity to the total?’. The former is more an
475 explorative question, while the latter is more an investigative question. While some
476 approaches may be applied to answer both questions (Direct CA, First Tier CA, and Path CA),
477 HEM and Life Cycle Stage CA are most useful for the last type of question, where the
478 practitioner wants to gain deeper insight into a specific part of their model. This will limit the
479 amount of use-cases HEM is relevant in LCA.

480 While we show that double counting cannot occur in HEM, this does require a comment on
481 the scope of this statement. Double counting cannot occur with a single extraction (whether
482 that is one or multiple processes), doing multiple different extractions, e.g. extracting two
483 different industry sectors separately or extracting a region and an industry sector would lead
484 to double counting due to the direct or indirect relationships between the processes in those
485 extractions and this should not be done. Such problems can be avoided by interpreting such
486 results independently from each other or combining the extractions into a single extraction.

487 Furthermore, a main limitation is that there are currently no standard software tools to apply
488 HEM in LCA for practitioners. However, we do share the code we used to apply HEM in our
489 ecoinvent example in van der Meide (2025). This could be modified into a more generic
490 software package in the future.

491 Next, one limitation that applies both to HEM and all other CA approaches; the usefulness
492 of the approach will entirely depend on the quality of the data used and whether that is
493 sufficient for the question at hand.

494 One more limitation comes when HEM in LCA is compared to HEM in IOA, in the latter, it is
495 often used to analyze trade relationships, through extracting regions (Miller & Lahr, 2001).
496 We also demonstrate this use-case in SI 1.7.2 and we do find that the insights this can
497 provide rely on the underlying data. Production location and trade data is not well
498 represented in LCI databases such as ecoinvent (Wernet et al., 2016). That said, especially
499 since version 3.10, ecoinvent has included more trade information in every version, so it
500 remains to be seen how much of a problem this will remain into the future.

501 Finally, changes to the technology matrix are made, this brings two possible questions. The
502 first is on stability of results, when looking closely at each of the cases to implement HEM in
503 LCA, it turns out each already has commonly used analogs in LCA and they pose no risk to
504 calculations, as discussed further in SI 1.5. The second is on the computational load of re-
505 calculating the scaling vector, one additional solution to the scaling vector needs to be
506 found for each HEM calculation, which common LCA software such as Brightway2 (Mutel,
507 2017) can do in well under a second, meaning that doing such a calculation twice should
508 not be an issue. Lastly, more exotic approaches to LCA such as dynamic LCA have not been
509 considered in this study, the interplay of such approaches to LCA and contribution analysis
510 should be studied in more detail.

511 5. Conclusion

512 In this study we introduced HEM from IOA as a useful CA approach in LCA and have shown
513 how HEM may provide different insights into LCA results compared to existing CA

514 approaches. Through our demonstration of HEM in a simplified example and a larger
515 example using ecoinvent (Wernet et al., 2016), we have shown how HEM can be used and
516 what insights it can provide in LCA. By comparing with several established CA approaches
517 we have shown how and when results are different and how this can help practitioners to
518 gain insight into results.

519 As we have shown, this approach can help practitioners gain deeper understanding of
520 impacts within their systems. The methodological connections between IOA and LCA
521 should keep being investigated by both sides to keep improving both methods.

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528

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532

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